

Stage 1 Registered Report

Decoding the Dorsal Stream's Role in Object Shape Recognition: A tractography-driven ccPAS Approach

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Abstract

Visual experience requires the orchestration of intricate brain connections. One of the most influential models of human visual information processing posits the existence of two segregated streams and postulates that conscious object recognition exclusively relies upon the ventral visual stream. However, recent evidence advocates for an involvement of the dorsal stream in encoding some crucial attributes for visual object recognition, such as global shape. Therefore, the specific role of the dorsal stream is controversial in this context. Through an individualized multimodal integrative approach, the present work will assess the contribution of the dorsal pathway in object recognition. Starting from MRI data, a protocol of individualized diffusion weighted imaging (DWI) tractography-based cortico-cortical paired associative stimulation protocol (ccPAS) will causally manipulate V1-to-IPS dorsal stream connectivity, by strengthening synaptic efficacy between targeted regions through Hebbian-like plasticity mechanisms. Providing causal insights into global shape processing may also help tailor rehabilitative interventions to maximize recovery after neural damage such as strokes or brain tumors affecting visual areas.

Keywords: dorsal visual pathway, global shape, transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS), DWI, connectivity.

Introduction

Human understanding of the physical world is deeply grounded in conscious perceptual experience, which is primarily visual. The brain's ability to quickly and accurately identify objects by sight is crucial for survival and allows us to interact effectively with our environment. Nonetheless, disentangling the complex neural dynamics underlying object recognition, a crucial aspect of conscious visual processing, poses a significant challenge in contemporary cognitive neuroscience. Both animal and human models of visual information processing have thus far associated the successful recognition of objects with the ventral visual pathway (Goodale & Milner, 1992; Milner & Goodale, 2008; Mishkin & Ungerleider, 1982). However, novel evidence highlights a possible involvement of the dorsal stream in computing some key attributes crucial for visual object recognition (Ayzenberg et al., 2023).

According to the influential model proposed by Milner and Goodale, the visual system is segregated into two anatomically independent streams originating in the early visual cortex (Goodale & Milner, 1992). The ventral stream (also called vision-for-perception) projects to the inferotemporal cortex and is thought to support the perceptual identification of objects. The dorsal stream (also called vision-for-action) projects to the posterior parietal cortex and is thought to be involved in sensorimotor transformations for visually guided actions. Moreover, the dorsal stream receives direct magnocellular projections from the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGN) that bypass V1 (Sincich et al., 2004). Despite being grounded in a long history of neuropsychological, single-unit, behavioral, and functional imaging findings, this clear-cut distinction between the two pathways is currently under discussion. Visual processing, indeed, has turned out to be more tangled than initially postulated by this model. Consistently with this scenario, the hypothesis that the dorsal stream has a crucial role in object recognition by computing some identity-relevant object attributes like depth, orientation, structure-from-motion, and shape independently of goal-directed actions has been supported by recent compelling findings (Ayzenberg & Behrmann, 2022a, 2022b; Erlikhman et al., 2018; Freud et al., 2020; Freud, Plaut, & Behrmann, 2016; Xu, 2018). Importantly, according to this perspective, the dorsal stream is thought to be directly involved in object recognition, and its role is not simply redundant with respect to the information processed in the ventral stream. In keeping with this hypothesis, neuropsychological literature documented several cases of object recognition deficits (i.e. agnosia) in patients with parietal damage (Dalrymple et al., 2007; Karnath et al., 2000; Riddoch et al., 2008; Riddoch & Humphreys, 1987; Thomas et al., 2012; Warrington & Taylor, 1973) and accumulating evidence of different nature, such as lesion studies in non-human primate (Tsutsui et al., 2001; Van Dromme et al., 2016), human neuroimaging results (Bracci & Op de Beeck, 2016; Freud et al., 2017; Georgieva et al., 2008; Konen & Kastner, 2008; Vaziri-Pashkam & Xu, 2019), neural network models (Ayzenberg & Behrmann, 2022a) and causal studies with transcranial magnetic stimulation (Bagattini et al., 2015; Mazzi et al., 2014; Romei et al., 2011; Zachariou et al., 2017; Zaretskaya et al., 2013), support the effector-independent perceptual representations in the dorsal stream.

In this scenario, the specific functional contribution of the dorsal stream to object recognition is controversial. Among the distinct operations involved in the complex process of visual object recognition, the ability to concurrently code the global shape with the local features of an object represents a necessary stage to appreciate its identity (Humphreys & Riddoch, 2006). Currently, a lively debate on object shape processing is unfolding between two opposite standpoints. On the one hand, the original proposal postulates that shape representation is uniquely supported by the ventral pathway without requiring any dorsal stream involvement (Goodale & Milner, 2023a, 2023b). On the other hand, this main-stream conceptualization is challenged by the idea that global shape processing is computed in the dorsal stream and just later conveyed to the ventral stream (Ayzenberg et al., 2023; Ayzenberg & Behrmann, 2022a, 2022b, 2023; Bracci & Op de Beeck, 2016; Freud, Plaut, & Behrmann, 2016).

A direct approach to causally probe the contribution of the dorsal stream in object shape recognition is to manipulate its synaptic strength by means of cortico-cortical paired associative stimulation

(ccPAS). ccPAS is a dual-site stimulation protocol in which pairs of transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) pulses are repeatedly delivered to two interconnected cortical regions at a specific time interval (i.e., inter-stimulus interval; ISI). ccPAS relies on Hebbian plasticity principles (Hebb D.O., 1949) which postulate that the repeated activation of a presynaptic cell A immediately before activation of postsynaptic cell B induces synaptic strengthening (i.e., long-term potentiation; LTP). ccPAS protocols are thought to promote spike-timing-dependent plasticity (STDP) which is associated with changes in the strength of effective cortico-cortical connectivity between targeted regions that can be measured through modulations in behavioral performance on tasks supported by the stimulated connections. Previous studies testified these dynamics in motor areas (Buch et al., 2011; Casarotto et al., 2023; Chao et al., 2015; Chiappini et al., 2020; Fiori et al., 2018; Rizzo et al., 2011; Turrini et al., 2022; Veniero et al., 2013). Crucially, recent studies provided evidence of the possibility of inducing plasticity in the visual system and boosting visual perception according to STDP mechanisms (for a recent review see Tarasi et al., 2024). Pioneered by the first application of ccPAS to investigate plasticity within the visual system (Romei et al., 2016), several studies targeted the V1-V5 network, critical for motion awareness, consistently demonstrating that ccPAS aimed at strengthening reentrant V5-to-V1 pathway significantly improved visual motion perception (Romei et al., 2016; Chiappini et al., 2018; Di Luzio et al., 2022; Bevilacqua et al., 2023). By targeting the ventral visual pathway, Borgomaneri and colleagues investigated the role of this occipito-temporal network in face perception and showed that the strengthening of the superior temporal sulcus (STS)-to-V1 connections led to enhanced visual sensitivity to facial expressions (Borgomaneri et al., 2023). In the same vein, the protocol we propose here targets the right primary visual cortex (V1), i.e., the starting point of the cortical visual pathways (Goodale & Milner, 1992), and the right intraparietal sulcus (IPS), a critical high-order key node of the dorsal visual stream that directly receives input from V1 (Greenberg et al., 2012). Notably, this parietal region has been demonstrated to show a selective activation, especially in the right hemisphere, for object-center part relations, which is an essential property for object recognition processes (e.g., Ayzenberg & Behrmann, 2022b; Goldstein-Marcusohn et al., 2024; Jeong & Xu, 2016; Zachariou et al., 2014). Recent findings (Wang et al., 2022) highlighted that the analysis of certain object properties computed in parietal regions might not require V1 when magnocellular input is available. Nevertheless, while subcortical projections may contribute to some aspects of visual object processing, this does not preclude the parallel involvement of the cortical pathway. This ccPAS protocol will allow us to determine whether the dorsal stream's role in global shape perception operates independently of other pathways, such as the ventral stream or subcortical magnocellular projections.

In this field, with high inter-individual variability in terms of observed effects being a critical issue, the selection of the cortical site to be targeted by TMS is of extreme importance. The vast majority of previously available studies adopted a "one-site-fits-all" targeting approach (Cash & Zalesky, 2023), which does not account for the substantial anatomical and functional brain variability that most likely affects the TMS efficacy (Cash et al., 2021; Menardi et al., 2022; Opitz et al., 2016). Critically, the implementation of personalized spatial targeting highlighted the superiority of individualized TMS approaches by maximizing network engagement (Lynch et al., 2022; Menardi et al., 2022; Menardi et al., 2022). This evidence is further supported by additional studies on the therapeutic application of TMS (Bagattini et al., 2021; Cash & Zalesky, 2023; Lynch et al., 2022).

In this perspective, advanced neuroimaging techniques, such as diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) using MRI, allow for in vivo human brain fiber tracking. Currently, DTI (Diffusion Tensor Imaging), originally formulated by Basser and colleagues (Basser et al., 1994), represents the most commonly used model for investigating white matter (WM) brain structure. It assesses the preferred direction of water diffusion along WM fiber tracts, known as anisotropy. Moreover, DTI allows the reconstruction of cerebral connectivity in vivo with the help of fiber tractography algorithms (Corbo et al., 2014). Crucially, TMS-induced signal propagation has been proven to engage structurally rather than functionally connected regions preferentially (Bortoletto et al., 2015; Momi et al., 2021).

Building on this, the approach we propose here capitalizes on the joint use of a ccPAS protocol (targeting the visual domain) and tractography measures characterizing the cortical and subcortical architecture at the individual level. For the first time, indeed, a personalized targeting approach driving the ccPAS protocol is introduced. Specifically, TMS targeting will be individually guided by the identification of specific WM tracts with the electric field focalized on their cortical projections. This approach will not only account for interindividual differences (Reisch et al., 2022) but will also improve TMS spatial resolution by effectively and accurately recruiting specific subcortical structures (Nummenmaa et al., 2014) with a potential key impact on ccPAS plasticity effects.

The main aim of the present work is to investigate the contribution of the dorsal visual stream in object recognition by strengthening V1-to-IPS dorsal stream connectivity through an individualized tractography-based ccPAS protocol. Specifically, we will employ a multimodal integrative approach (see Fig. 1) that takes advantage of the integration of a causal manipulative approach (i.e., ccPAS) with anatomo-structural (i.e., DTI) measures to delve into the role of the dorsal visual pathway in object global shape processing. According to our main hypothesis, if the dorsal stream is directly contributing to global shape processing, we expect to find an increase in the discrimination of global shape (H 1.1 – see “Design Table”) as a consequence of the ccPAS-induced strengthening of V1-IPS connectivity. The behavioral effect observed in the experimental V1-IPS ccPAS condition will be compared with that of two control ccPAS conditions in order to assess the temporal specificity of the effect and to control for potential confounding factors. Additional control conditions will be conducted in order to test the functional specificity of the ccPAS behavioral effect (i.e., task specificity and attention-related processing).

Methods

Ethics information

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the local ethical committee (Comitato Etico Territoriale Area Sud-Ovest Veneto - CET-ASOV; approval number 371CET). Written informed consent will be obtained from all participants before data collection. They will be reimbursed for their participation on an hourly basis. The study will be performed in accordance with the ethical standard of the 2013 Declaration of Helsinki. Participants will be recruited through word of mouth, as well as through a combination of printed and electronic advertisements displayed on notice boards at the University of Verona, where the study will be conducted (Perception and Awareness (Panda) lab).

Sampling plan

Sample size calculation was performed with G*Power software (v. 3.1.9.7), with a power of 95% and a level of significance of 5%. The sample size estimation was performed for the primary research question (Q1: Does the strengthening of dorsal stream connectivity modulate global shape representation?) and specifically on H1.1, which aims at investigating the effect of V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS protocol on global shape discrimination as compared to control ccPAS protocols (i.e., V1-IPS 0ms and V1-IPS 30ms). Because in the literature, no studies tested the efficacy of V1-IPS ccPAS on shape discrimination, the sample size was determined based on a recent study using ccPAS to induce plastic changes in the visual pathways in order to investigate the effects on perceptual sensitivity (Di Luzio et al., 2022). To estimate the power needed to detect the main effect of within-subjects "ccPAS condition" (V1-IPS 9ms; V1-IPS 0ms; V1-IPS 30ms) on baseline corrected (post ccPAS-pre ccPAS) behavioral variables, we considered the significant main effect of ccPAS condition on the difference in motion sensitivity threshold in Di Luzio and colleagues paper (post ccPAS-baseline; $F(2,48)=6.51$,

Figure 1 | Experimental design a. Schematic overview of the experimental design procedure. It consists of four experimental sessions divided into as many days. Firstly, an MRI acquisition will be acquired (T1 and DWI sequence). In the last three sessions, participants will undergo three ccPAS protocols delivered in a counterbalanced order across participants. Before and immediately after the ccPAS protocol, a two-alternative forced-choice match-to-sample task will be delivered. **b.** The three different ccPAS conditions. Each participant will take part in all the conditions on three different days. Each session will consist of 180 paired pulses delivered at a rate of 0.2 Hz for 15 minutes, at 120% of the individual rMT. On the left, the V1-IPS 9ms condition, which is expected to modulate the dorsal stream by stimulating right V1 (i.e., first TMS pulse) and right IPS (i.e., second TMS pulse) with an inter-stimulus interval (ISI) of 9ms is represented. In the middle, the V1-IPS 0ms condition (first control condition), planned to account for possible nonspecific effects induced by the TMS. The TMS pulses will be delivered simultaneously over the right V1 and right IPS (ISI 0ms); according to the Hebbian principle, no modulation is expected here. On the right, the V1-IPS 30ms condition (second control condition), designed to prove the time specificity of the effect, is represented. The right V1 and right IPS will be targeted with an ISI of 30ms. Arrows (when present) indicate the direction of the ccPAS-induced plasticity for the experimental (green) and control (orange) conditions.

Behavioral task

Participants will be tested in a dimly illuminated test room before and after each ccPAS protocol with the same behavioral procedure. They will sit in front of a 24 in. ASUS monitor (resolution 1920x1080, refresh rate 144Hz) placed at a viewing distance of 57 cm, with the head laying on an adaptable chin rest to align the participant's eyes to the center of the screen.

A modified 2-alternative forced choice (2AFC) match-to-sample discrimination task will be employed (see Fig. 2a) (adapted from Chouinard and colleagues-Chouinard et al., 2017). Visual stimuli will consist of 3D elongated geons composed of parts with different local features (see Fig. 2b) that can be arranged in several spatial configurations and shown from several observation points (modified from a previously used stimuli dataset, Ayzenberg & Behrmann, 2022b). Those stimuli are chosen to facilitate a response along the dorsal stream, due to their properties in evoking a visuo-motor response (Freud et al., 2020; Marini et al., 2019) and due to the sensibility of the dorsal stream to changes in visual stimuli (James et al., 2002; Valyear et al., 2006) independently from task demands. This is essential for our protocol since the effectiveness of the ccPAS procedure also depends on the engagement of the network of interest. Participants will be asked to specify which of two stimuli matched the sample stimulus in terms of spatial arrangement (hereafter called "global shape task") or in terms of local features (hereafter called "local features task"). Pilot data (see the Behavioral task pilot paragraph) demonstrated that the two tasks are comparable in terms of difficulty since no differences between the global shape task and the local features task were found in accuracy, RTs, and d' .

Each behavioral session will comprise 1 training block of 36 trials and 8 experimental blocks of 36 trials each for a total of 288 trials (120 "Global shape task" trials, 120 "Local features task" trials, 24 "Global shape task" catch trials, and 24 "Local features task" catch trials). The entire behavioral session will last 21 minutes.

In each trial, one sample and two items-to-match will be presented. In the "Global shape task" trials, items-to-match can be either totally incongruent with the local features of the sample (i.e. all items' local features are different from the sample's local features), or partially incongruent (i.e., at least one item shares a feature with the sample). In the "Local features task" trials, both the items-to-match have a different global shape than the sample, and the incorrect item can be either totally incongruent with the features of the sample, or partially incongruent, sharing only one feature with it.

Each trial will begin with the presentation of a central fixation cross on a dark gray screen for 500 ms (1.62 cm/m²), then a central stimulus (sample image) will be presented for 75 ms (2.3°x4.3°; 8.03 cm/m²) on the fixation cross. After an interval of 116 ms (in order to avoid the fusion of the stimuli), two central items-to-match will be presented for 75 ms above and under the fixation cross at 4.5° eccentricity from central fixation. After 416 ms, a central green circle will be displayed for 150 ms to inform the participants about the task to be performed: a large green circle (8.4° in diameter, matching the size of the global target) will indicate the “Global shape task” while a small green circle (2.8° in diameter, corresponding to the dimension of the local features) will indicate the “Local features task”. After the circle onset, participants will be asked to report as fast and accurately as possible which stimulus was the one that shares with the sample image the characteristic required in the task (i.e., global shape or local features) by pressing two vertical keys on a response box, standing for the upper or above stimulus. A variable randomized interval, lasting between 1500 and 2000 ms, is left for the response before the start of the next trial. The position of the correct item-to-match will be randomized across trials. The order of trials (i.e., “Global shape” task and “Local features” task) will be randomized within each block. Different local features and different spatial configurations of objects will be balanced across trials considering both sample images and items-to-match. Participants will rest for 30 s during inter-block intervals until a 3 s countdown highlights the beginning of the following block. The response will be delivered by using the left and the right index finger respectively on the two vertical keys. The position of the fingers will be reversed halfway through the task and the starting order of fingers will be balanced across participants. Both reaction times (RTs) and accuracy (percentage of correct responses) will be recorded. The stimuli duration and the intervals between them were tested by means of a photodiode and an oscilloscope.

Before starting, participants will be instructed about the type of stimuli used (i.e., elongated geons) and the structure of the trial sequence. Some examples of the two types of tasks are presented to elucidate the definition of global shape and local features and to describe the task selection by means of the two different circles (large green for global shape and small green for local features, respectively).

Figure 2 | Behavioral task. a. The trial structure of the modified 2-alternative forced choice (2AFC) match-to-sample discrimination task. Participants will be asked to report which of the two items displayed matches the sample previously seen by discriminating the global shape or the features of the objects. The task starts by asking the participant to maintain the gaze on the fixation cross. After 500 ms, the sample appears in the center of the screen for 75 ms. After 116 ms two items to match appear above and under the fixation cross for 75 ms. After an interval of 416 ms, around the fixation cross, a circle appears for 150 ms revealing the task to be computed: a big green circle for the “Global

shape task”, and a small green circle for the “Local features task”. For the response, a random interval lasting between 1500-2000 ms will be left. **b.** The properties of the different types of trials. For each task, trials can be divided into “Totally incongruent” trials and “Partially incongruent trials”. The incongruency is based on the presence of the features of the sample in the items to match. In totally incongruent trials of the global shape task, the items to match have all the features different from the sample, while in the local features task, only the incorrect item has all the features different from the sample. In partially incongruent trials of the global shape task one feature in each item or in only one item can be shared with the sample, while in the local features task, only the incorrect item can share one feature with the sample. The correct response is highlighted in white. The red square highlights the critical properties that characterize the incongruency of the items-to-match with the sample (“Totally incongruent trials” vs “Partially incongruent trials”).

MRI acquisition

All participants will undergo an MRI session before the ccPAS sessions. Anatomical images will be acquired with a 3T Philips Ingenia with a 32-channel head RF receive coils. MRI images will include: (i) 3D T1-weighted (T1w) Turbo-field echo image (1mm-isotropic TE/TR=3.8/8.4 ms, TI=1050 ms), (ii) diffusion-weighted (DWI) data (2mm-isotropic, TE/TR=126/6000ms, shells: $b = \{0, 1000, 2000\}$ s/mm, 12/32/64 directions).

MRI pre-processing

All participant T1w images will go through standard preprocessing steps: (i) raw DICOM T1-w images will be converted to Nifti format using dcm2nii software (Li et al., 2016); (ii) AC-PC (Anterior-Posterior Commissures) alignment will be performed by means of rigid registration to the MNI152 T1-w template (Avants et al., 2008); (iii) brain mask will be estimated (Avants et al., 2014) and used to perform the Bias-Field Correction restricted on brain voxels only (N4-Bias Field Correction tool; Tustison et al., 2010); (v) segmentation into 6 brain tissues will be performed with several algorithms (Amorosino et al., 2020; Çiçek et al., 2016; Ronneberger et al., 2015; Smith et al., 2012) to then establish the best performing one for accurate estimation of the tractogram given peculiarities of dorsal/occipital regions); (vi) finally, a synthetic T2-w image will be created using AFNI toolkit (Cox, 1996).

DWI data will be preprocessed using combinations of MRtrix3 commands (Tournier et al., 2012) in conjunction with FSL (Jenkinson et al., 2012). Images will be corrected for thermal noise, Eddy currents and Gibbs ringing. By applying diffeomorphic registration to the susceptibility-induced echo-planar imaging (EPI) of the DWIs volumes, and by using a combination of data from an undistorted structural MRI and DWI reversed-phase encoding directions (i.e., AP and PA acquisitions), distortion correction will be introduced. Further correction will be applied to control for bias field inhomogeneities (Tustison et al., 2010) on DWI data.

Reconstructions of streamlines will be carried out using the MRtrix3 program (Tournier et al., 2012). The WM fiber Orientation Distribution Function (fODF) will be obtained from the estimation of the response function using the Dhollander method (Dhollander et al., 2016) by applying the multi-shell, multi-tissue Constrained Spherical Deconvolution (CSD, Jeurissen et al., 2014) ($l_{max}=6$; $threshold=0.5$). In order to confine the streamlines' length between 20 and 250 millimeters and to halt the tracking process after choosing at least 10 million streamlines, probabilistic anatomically-constrained tractography, or ACT, will be calculated using CSD (cutoff 0.06). The SIFT2 technique will be then used to guarantee that the tractogram was correctly filtered and to counteract overfitting (Smith et al., 2015).

Tract dissection and neuronavigation

Once the fully masked tractogram is obtained, it will be processed in TrackVis to dissect the V1-IPS tract of interest, representing the dorsal stream. Seed regions of interest (ROIs) will be identified based on a combination of anatomical and atlas-based approaches to ensure precision and reproducibility. First, the IPS ROI will be anatomically localized using individual T1-weighted images. To account for cortical variability across participants, we will co-register the Wang atlas regions (Wang et al., 2015) to each subject's native space. This atlas provides a reliable anatomical framework for identifying IPS regions. By overlaying the atlas on individual brains, we ensure that the identified ROIs are contained within the predefined IPS regions from the atlas. This step will minimize user-related variability and provide consistency in anatomical placement. While anatomical localization will be prioritized, we acknowledge the importance of functional definitions in cases of significant cortical variability, as highlighted by Ayzenberg & Behrmann (2022b). After atlas-based co-registration, manual inspection will be performed to refine ROI placement based on individual anatomical variations visible in T1-weighted images. This will ensure that seed regions are accurately positioned for tractography while adhering to anatomical landmarks. The identified cortical origins of the bundles (Tagliaferri et al., 2023) will then be used as targets for ccPAS protocols by means of a neuronavigation system (SofTaxis software v.3.4, EMS, Italy). Individual T1w images will be used for stereotaxic frameless neuronavigation, by means of an optical infrared camera and reflective markers placed on the participant's head and TMS coil. To obtain population-level localization of the stimulation sites, the individual brains will be then normalized in MNI space and target coordinates will be extracted (Fig.3).

Figure 3 | DWI Pipeline. Description of relevant pre-processing and fitting steps of MRI processing are reported. Data from a single subject are presented: (i) In the first column, DWI preprocessed images b0-images and tensor DTI (Diffusion Tensor Imaging) fitting FA (Fractional Anisotropy) maps are displayed; (ii) In the second column, T1-weighted skull-stripped pre-processed image and segmentation results are displayed together with the representation of the white-matter (WM) boundary; (iii) Visual representation of FOD (Fiber Orientation Distribution) is reported (Tournier et al., 2019) together with the tractogram at the individual level derived from the anatomically constrained tractography (ACT).

TMS parameter definition

Stimulation intensity will be defined according to the individual resting motor threshold (rMT), which will be determined at the beginning of each session. Electromyographic activity will be visualized online by means of a bipolar belly-tendon montage of the first dorsal interosseous (FDI) muscle of the left hand using Ag/AgCl pre-gelled surface electrodes. The active recording electrode will be placed over the muscle belly, and the reference electrode on the proximal phalanx bone of the index finger. The ground electrode will be placed over the forearm. The motor hotspot of the left FDI muscle will be identified in the right hemisphere as the area eliciting the highest and most reliable motor-evoked potentials (MEPs) with the same TMS intensity by moving the coil in 0.5 cm steps around the motor hand area. Then, the individual rMT will be defined as the minimum TMS intensity (expressed as the percentage of maximum stimulator output) able to elicit a MEP of at least 50 μ V by employing the parameter estimation by sequential testing (PEST) procedure (Awiszus, 2003; Dissanayaka et al., 2018) (i.e., maximum-likelihood threshold-hunting approach). The coils will be placed tangentially on the surface of the scalp. V1 stimulation on the right hemisphere will be performed by placing the coil at an angle of 120 degrees (Chiappini et al., 2018; Di Luzio et al., 2022; Romei et al., 2016). For the right IPS stimulation, the coil will be oriented with an angle of about 60 degrees counterclockwise, thus maintaining the same orientation between the two coils (Di Luzio et al., 2022). Neuronavigation software (SofTaxis, E.M.S., Bologna, Italy) combined with a 3D optical digitizer (Polaris Vicra, NDI, Waterloo, Canada) will allow us to save the coil positions for the ccPAS sessions.

ccPAS protocols

Participants will undergo an experimental ccPAS protocol, targeting dorsal stream connectivity (V1-IPS 9ms), and two control ccPAS protocols, to control for the nonspecific TMS effects (V1-IPS 0ms) and the temporal specificity (V1-IPS 30ms) of the protocol. The order of the ccPAS protocols will be counterbalanced across participants.

The ccPAS protocols will be delivered using two 50 mm custom-made figure-of-eight coated coils connected to a Magstim BiStim² stimulator (Magstim Company, UK). 180 paired pulses will be delivered at a rate of 0.2 Hz for a total duration of about 15 minutes, with each pair consisting of two monophasic transcranial magnetic pulses. TMS intensity will be set at 120% of the individual resting motor threshold (rMT) for both conditioning and test pulses as done in previous ccPAS studies targeting parietal areas (Casula et al., 2016; Guidali et al., 2023; Nord et al., 2019; Santarnecchi et al., 2018; Zibman et al., 2019). Neuronavigation software (SofTaxis, E.M.S., Bologna, Italy) combined with a 3D optical digitizer (Polaris Vicra, NDI, Waterloo, Canada) will be used throughout the experiment to maintain the coils' position over the participant's head within a 2-mm accuracy threshold. Participants will be asked to maintain their gaze on a central yellow fixation cross and to mentally count the number of times it changed into purple (i.e., ten times during the protocol) to avoid sleepiness and keep their attention high during the ccPAS – a critical condition for protocols' effectiveness (Stefan et al., 2000). TMS pulses and trial presentation will be controlled with E-Prime 3.0 (Psychology Software Tools Inc., Pittsburgh, PA, USA).

Experimental ccPAS protocol targeting dorsal stream connectivity from V1 to IPS (V1-IPS 9ms): TMS pulses will be delivered over V1, unanimously considered as the origin of the dorsal stream, and IPS, a critical parietal cortical region along the dorsal stream. Both pulses will be delivered over the right hemisphere. Indeed, right IPS has been demonstrated to be engaged in processing object properties relevant for recognition and an increasing body of evidence shows a selective activation for object-center part relations (Ayzenberg & Behrmann, 2022b; Bracci & Op de Beeck, 2016; Freud, Plaut, & Behrmann Marlene, 2016; Goldstein-Marcusohn et al., 2024; Jeong & Xu, 2016; Zachariou et al., 2014). The stimulation sites (i.e., right V1 and right IPS) will be identified using tractography-based individualized cortical sites (see the "MRI pre-processing" paragraph). Coils' orientation is described

above (see the “Transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) parameter definition” paragraph). The conditioning TMS pulse (i.e., first) will be delivered over V1, while the test TMS pulse (i.e., second) will be delivered over the IPS with an ISI of 9ms. The critical ISI has been chosen based on a previous electrocorticographic (ECoG) recording study aimed at estimating the spatiotemporal dynamics of visual information processing along the human posterior cortex (Regev et al., 2018).

Control ccPAS protocol targeting dorsal stream connectivity from V1 to IPS (V1-IPS 0ms): In order to test possible nonspecific effects induced by the TMS, a control ccPAS protocol with ISI 0ms will be employed. In this protocol, the target areas will be the same as in V1-IPS 9ms condition but the pulses will be delivered simultaneously (ISI= 0ms). According to the Hebbian principles (Hebb D.O., 1949), synaptic efficacy increases if the presynaptic neuron persistently takes part in the firing of the postsynaptic target neuron. However, if two neurons fire at the same time, then one cannot have caused or taken part in the firing of the other (Caporale & Dan, 2008; Romei et al., 2016). Thus, no net spike-timing dependent plasticity is expected following the V1-IPS 0ms ccPAS condition.

Control ccPAS protocol dorsal stream connectivity from V1 to IPS (V1-IPS 30ms): In order to test the temporal specificity of the experimental V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS condition, a control ccPAS protocol will be employed. In this protocol, the target areas will be the same as in V1-IPS 9ms condition but the pulses will be delivered with a 30ms ISI. This ISI has been chosen on the basis of a previous study (Di Luzio et al., 2022) that tested the same connection in the opposite direction (IPS-V1), finding an improvement in metacognition.

Analysis plan

Statistical analysis will be performed using Jamovi (Version 2.3.28; The Jamovi Project, 2024). Statistical significance will be set at $p < 0.05$.

Behavioral data: For each participant, trials with RTs < 150 ms will be considered unreliable answers, discarded, and not considered for further analysis.

Discrimination performance will be indexed by the accuracy and reaction time (RTs) values. Both measures will be calculated for each participant separately for “Global shape task” trials and “Local features task” trials, dividing “Totally incongruent” and “Partially incongruent” trials. The normality of accuracy and RTs data will be assessed by means of the Shapiro-Wilk test. In case data will not satisfy the properties of normal distribution, data will be transformed according to the commonly used transformations of continuous data: square root, base-ten logarithmic, and inverse transformation. The transformation showing the best fit to a normal distribution will be assessed through visual inspection of data distribution.

Additionally, in order to obtain a measure of accuracy not affected by the response bias, we will calculate d' sensitivity measure as assessed by signal detection theory (Macmillan & Creelman, 1991). d' will be calculated for each participant separately for “Global shape task” trials and “Local features task” trials, and for “Totally incongruent” and “Partially incongruent” trials, by subtracting the standardized false alarm rate of responses from the standardized hit rate as follows:

$$d' = z(\text{Hit rate}) - z(\text{False Alarm rate})$$

These rates correspond to probabilities on the normal distribution, therefore $z(\text{Hit rate})$ and $z(\text{False Alarm rate})$ are the z-scores that correspond to the normal distribution’s tail p-values represented by Hit and False Alarm. Task response accuracy in the modified 2AFC task will be scored as in Borgomaneri and colleagues (2023). Correct responses will be considered as follows: an “up” response when the correct item-to-match is presented at the top of the screen will count as a “hit” whereas a “down” response when the correct item-to-match is presented at the bottom of the screen will count as a correct rejection. Incorrect responses will be considered as follows: an “up” response when the correct item-to-match is presented at the bottom of the screen will be counted as a false alarm, whereas a

“down” response when the correct item is at the top of the screen will be considered a miss. In order to further control for a possible response bias (outcome neutral test/positive control), the SDT criterion index c will be calculated. The criterion index reflects the participants’ tendency to favor one response over another in a 2AFC discrimination task.

c will be calculated for each participant for “Global shape task” trials, by averaging the standardized hit rate of responses and the standardized false alarm rate as follows:

$$c = - \frac{[z(\text{Hit rate}) + z(\text{False Alarm rate})]}{2}$$

Design Table 1 provides a detailed overview of the analyses for all the outlined research questions.

Question 1. Does the strengthening of dorsal stream connectivity modulate global shape representation?

Hypothesis 1.1 If the dorsal pathway is directly involved in object shape recognition, we expect to find a greater effect on behavioral performance in the global shape task after the experimental V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS condition as a consequence of the strengthening of the dorsal stream connectivity.

In order to test whether strengthening dorsal pathway connectivity through V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS protocol induces a greater effect in global shape discrimination performance as compared to control ccPAS conditions, separate repeated measures ANOVA on baseline corrected (post ccPAS- pre ccPAS) accuracy, RTs and d' values of “Global shape task” trials with “ccPAS condition” (3 levels: V1-IPS 9ms; V1-IPS 0ms; V1-IPS 30ms) and “Incongruency” (2 levels: “Totally incongruent” trials; “Partially incongruent” trials) as within-subjects factors will be performed.

Hypothesis 1.2 The effect on behavioral performance for the discrimination of global shape after the experimental V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS protocol is not due to a change in participants’ response bias.

In order to verify that the effect on discrimination performance after V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS protocol is not due to a change in participants’ response criterion, a repeated measures ANOVA on baseline corrected (post ccPAS- pre ccPAS) c values of “Global shape task” trials with “ccPAS condition” (3 levels: V1-IPS 9ms; V1-IPS 0ms; V1-IPS 30ms) as within-subjects factor will be performed.

Hypothesis 1.3 If the dorsal pathway is directly involved in object shape recognition, after the experimental V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS protocol we expect to find a greater increase in behavioral performance for the discrimination of global shape as compared to the discrimination of local features.

In order to verify the task specificity of the increase in discrimination performance after each ccPAS protocol (i.e. V1-IPS 9ms; V1-IPS 0ms; V1-IPS 30ms), a repeated measures ANOVA will be performed on both baseline corrected (post ccPAS-pre ccPAS) accuracy, RTs and d' values of all trials (Global shape task and Local features task trials) with “Task” (2 levels: “Global shape task” and “Local features task”), “ccPAS condition” (3 levels: V1-IPS 9ms; V1-IPS 0ms; V1-IPS 30ms) and “Incongruency” (2 levels: “Totally incongruent” trials; “Partially incongruent” trials) as within-subjects factors.

In all the statistical analyses so far reported (H1.1, H1.2, H1.3), the Greenhouse-Geisser correction will be applied when appropriate. Partial eta squared will be computed and reported as a measure of effect size for the main effects, whereas Cohen’s d will be computed and reported for post-hoc comparisons. To account for multiple comparisons, when necessary, significant p -values will be

corrected using false discovery rate (FDR) with the Benjamini–Hochberg procedure (Benjamini, 2010) (adjusted p value <0.05).

Data availability

Upon acceptance of the stage 2 registered report, we will share all raw and processed anonymized data as well as study materials publicly available as open data. Pilot raw and processed data can be found on this link:

https://osf.io/84caq/?view_only=284fab1192d7452d96b99f6ebe7907fc

Code availability

Analysis code will be made publicly available upon acceptance of the stage 2 registered report. Employed pipelines can be found on this link:

https://osf.io/84caq/?view_only=284fab1192d7452d96b99f6ebe7907fc

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Author contributions

EB Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization; **FS** Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization; **EP** Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Revision - Visualization; **AT** Methodology, Software, Investigation; **NC** Methodology, Software, Investigation; **FBP** Methodology, Investigation, Resources; **SFS** Methodology, Software, Revision; **DB** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing; **SS** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Funding acquisition; **DC** Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Resources, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization; **CM** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition; **CB** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Table 1. Design Table

Question	Hypothesis	Sampling Plan (N, power analysis)	Analysis Plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hp	Interpretation given to different outcomes	Theory that could be shown wrong by the outcomes
<p>Q1) Does the strengthening of dorsal stream connectivity modulate object shape recognition?</p>	<p>H1.1) If the dorsal pathway is directly involved in object shape recognition, we expect to find a greater effect on behavioral performance in the global shape task after the experimental V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS condition (as compared to the ccPAS control conditions) as a consequence of the strengthening of the dorsal stream connectivity.</p> <p><i>(Outcome neutral test/positive control: nonspecific TMS effects and temporal specificity)</i></p>	<p>Sample size calculation was performed with G*Power software (v. 3.1.9.7), with a power of 95% and a significance level of 5%. To estimate the power needed to detect the main effect of "ccPAS condition" (V1-IPS 9 ms; V1-IPS 0 ms; V1-IPS 30ms), we considered the significant main effect of ccPAS condition on the difference in motion sensitivity threshold reported in the study by Di Luzio and colleagues (Di Luzio et al., 2022 PLoS Biology) (post ccPAS-baseline; $F_{2,48}=6.51$, $p=0.003$; partial eta square=0.21) and tested for a within factors repeated measures ANOVA. The estimated sample size resulted in 32</p>	<p>Repeated measures ANOVA on baseline corrected (post ccPAS-pre ccPAS) accuracy, RTs, d' values of "Global shape" trials with "ccPAS condition" (3 levels: V1-IPS 9ms; V1-IPS 0ms; V1-IPS 30ms) and "Incongruency" (2 levels: "Totally incongruent" trials; "Partially incongruent" trials) as within-subjects factors.</p>	<p>Since no studies tested the efficacy of V1-IPS ccPAS on shape recognition, the effect size was determined based on a recent study using ccPAS to induce plastic changes in the visual pathways in order to investigate the effects on perceptual sensitivity (Di Luzio et al, 2022 PLoS Biology). In that study, the main effect of the ccPAS condition and statistical analysis are similar to our H1.1.</p>	<p>A significant "ccPAS condition" main effect showing a greater effect on discriminating global shape after V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS compared to the control ccPAS protocols will support the involvement of the dorsal stream in global shape representation.</p> <p>V1-IPS 0ms ccPAS protocol will represent a control condition accounting for possible <i>nonspecific TMS effects</i>. Indeed, 0 ms ccPAS condition is largely adopted as a control condition known to have no effects on behavioral performance. Furthermore, <i>temporal specificity</i> will be controlled by stimulating the same targets using a 30ms ISI.</p> <p>The absence of a significant "ccPAS condition" main effect will not confirm the H1.1 hypothesis and H1.2 and H1.3 will not be tested.</p>	<p>A significant "ccPAS condition" main effect showing a greater effect on discriminating global shape after V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS compared to the control ccPAS protocols would pose evidence in contrast with the view that object shape representation is uniquely supported by the ventral pathway without requiring any dorsal stream involvement (Goodale & Milner, 2023; Goodale & Milner, 2023), and would support the direct contribution of the dorsal stream in object shape recognition (Ayzenberg & Behrmann, 2022a, 2022b; Ayzenberg et al., 2023; Ayzenberg & Behrmann, 2023;</p>

		participants (critical F= 3.145; actual power= 0.953). The result sample size estimation is consistent with a recent meta-analysis on ccPAS studies targeting the visual system (Di Luzio et al., 2024).			The absence of a significant “Incongruency” main effect will support the appropriateness of our task.	Bracci and De Beeck 2016; Freud et al., 2016).
	<p>H 1.2) The effect on behavioral performance for the discrimination of global shape after the experimental V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS protocol is not due to a change in participants’ response bias.</p> <p><i>(Outcome neutral test/positive control: <u>effect on response bias</u>)</i></p>	Sample size calculation has been performed considering H1.1.	Repeated measures ANOVA on baseline corrected (post ccPAS-pre ccPAS) response criterion c values of “Global shape” trials with “ccPAS condition” (3 levels: V1-IPS 9ms; V1-IPS 0ms; V1-IPS 30ms) as within-subjects factor.	The effect size for power analysis was determined considering H1.1.	A significant “ccPAS condition” main effect showing a greater shift in response criterion when discriminating global shape after V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS compared to the control ccPAS protocols, will NOT sustain H1.2. In this case, it will be discussed the effect of response criterion’s shift on the primary outcome measures (accuracy, RTs, ΔE and d') and how this shift may impact the interpretation of H1.1.	-
	<p>H1.3) If the dorsal pathway is directly involved in object shape recognition, after the experimental V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS protocol, we expect to find a greater effect on behavioral</p>	Sample size calculation has been performed considering H1.1.	Repeated measures ANOVA on baseline corrected (post ccPAS-pre ccPAS) accuracy, RTs, and d’ values with ccPAS condition” (3	The effect size for power analysis was determined considering H1.1.	A statistically significant difference showing a greater improvement in global shape discrimination as compared to local feature discrimination will support the <u>task specificity</u> of the V1-IPS 9ms ccPAS protocol.	A statistically significant difference showing a greater improvement in global shape discrimination as compared to local feature discrimination in our critical condition would pose evidence

	<p>performance for the discrimination of global shape as compared to the discrimination of local features.</p> <p><i>(Outcome neutral test/positive control: <u>Task specificity and attention-related processing</u>)</i></p>		<p>levels: V1-IPS 9ms; V1-IPS 0ms; V1-IPS 30ms), “Task” (2 levels: “Global shape task” and “Local features task”), and “Incongruency” (2 levels: “Totally incongruent” trials; “Partially incongruent” trials) as within-subjects factor.</p>		<p>As the dorsal stream is also known to play an important role in visual attention (Corbetta and Shulman, 2002*), task specificity will allow to rule out the possibility that the improvement in global shape discrimination is due to attention-related processing modulation.</p> <p>The absence of a statistically significant difference could be interpreted and will be discussed as possible:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - involvement of the dorsal stream in both global shape and local features representation; -evidence of the fact that local features have been computed as global shape; -evidence of an attentional/arousal effect due to IPS potentiation. The absence of a significant “Incongruency” main effect will support the appropriateness of our task. 	<p>in contrast with the view that object shape representation is uniquely supported by the ventral pathway without requiring any dorsal stream involvement (Goodale & Milner, 2023; Goodale & Milner, 2023), and would support the direct contribution of the dorsal stream in object shape recognition (Ayzenberg & Behrmann, 2022a, 2022b; Ayzenberg et al., 2023; Ayzenberg & Behrmann, 2023; Bracci and De Beeck 2016; Freud et al., 2016).</p>
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*Corbetta, M., Shulman, G. (2002). Control of goal-directed and stimulus-driven attention in the brain. Nat Rev Neurosci 3, 201–215. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn755>

Supplementary information

Pilot data

Behavioral pilot

The behavioral task (see the “Behavioral task” section) has been pilot-tested with a group of participants in order to refine and validate its capability to assess comparable performance between global shape and feature trials and to avoid ceiling or floor effects. A total of twenty-seven participants (26 right-handed, 1 corrected left-handed; 15 females and 12 males; mean age \pm standard deviation 24.5 years \pm 4.9) were tested, all reporting normal or corrected-to-normal visual acuity and no history of neurological or psychiatric disorders. One participant was not included because of technical problems that prevented the completion of the task. According to the exclusion criteria (see the “Exclusion criteria” section), 12 participants were excluded from the sample because showing an accuracy below chance according to the one-tailed binomial test (59.38% accuracy, $n=96$, $p=0.041$). 14 participants (13 right-handed, 1 correct left-handed; 5 females and 9 males; mean age \pm standard deviation 24.8 years \pm 5.7) were then included in the final sample of the pilot analysis. According to the Shapiro-Wilk test, the distribution of both mean RTs and accuracy showed a normal distribution ($W=0.929$, $p=0.295$; $W=0.919$, $p=0.21$). To validate our task prior to implementing the analysis plan, we conducted some statistical analysis on behavioral measures. Accuracy, RTs, and d' values were analyzed using three 2x2 repeated measures ANOVAs with Task (“Global shape task” trials; “Local features task” trials) and Incongruency of the items-to-match with the sample (totally incongruent; partially incongruent) as within-subjects factors. No significant main effects were found in both analyses. Results showed a significant Task x Incongruency interaction for accuracy ($F(1,13)=16.744$, $p=0.001$, $\eta^2=0.563$). Bonferroni-corrected post-hoc analysis showed that the performance in the “Global shape task” did not differ between totally and partially incongruent trials, whereas in the “Local features task” emerged a significant difference ($p=0.002$; see supplementary Fig. 1a). ANOVA on d' values showed a significant main effect of “Incongruency” ($F(1,13)=15.51$, $p=0.002$, $\eta^2=0.544$) and a significant Task x Incongruency interaction ($F(1,13)=5.08$, $p=0.042$, $\eta^2=0.281$), where bonferroni-corrected post-hoc comparisons showed a significant difference between totally and partially incongruent trials for the “Local features task” only ($p<0.001$; see supplementary Fig. 1c). These findings suggest that the spatial configuration (i.e., global shape) is processed independently of the local features in “Global shape task”. Finally, a two-tailed paired-samples t-test on c values comparing the two tasks attested no significant difference ($t(13)=0.014$, $p=0.989$, Cohen’s $d=0.003$; see supplementary Fig. 1d). To conclude, our pilot data show that we can reliably measure the behavioral performance concerning global shape and local feature tasks, that the performance is comparable, and no ceiling or floor effects occurred.

Supplementary Figure 1 | Behavioral pilot results (n=14) Graphical representation of results divided for “Global shape task” trials and “Local features task” trials reporting: **a.** Accuracy; **b.** Reaction Times; **c.** d' values; **d.** c values. Colored dots represent single-subject data, gray dots represent the mean value for each condition.

DWI pilot

The MRI acquisition protocol and the MRI preprocessing pipeline have been pilot-tested with one participant in order to verify the parameters of anatomical images acquisition, to shape the pipeline based on acquired signal, and to validate the feasibility of the whole protocol. The MRI acquisition protocol succeeded in acquiring a 3D T1-weighted (T1w) Turbo-field echo image and diffusion-weighted (DWI) data. Moreover, the pipeline analysis, with all the standardized pre-processing steps described in the “Materials and Methods” section, was successfully applied. The employed IPS ROI was correctly contained within the selected atlas regions. The reconstruction of the tract of interest in the subject space was successfully performed in TrackVis (as displayed in supplementary Fig. 2).

Supplementary Figure 2 | DWI pilot results (n=1). Visual representation of anatomical dissection of WM bundle of interest for tractography-informed neuronavigation in a single subject.